

Systematic Review: Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) based Load Balancing for Cloud Computing

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Abstract

In this modern era, the widespread use of cloud computing has led to a massive spike in users' requests. The infrastructure's resources would either not be able to handle the increased volume of traffic or the scenario would lead to some resources being over or underutilized. Due to the unpredictable spike in traffic, the system's performance eventually degrades. Optimal load distribution is a critical aspect of traffic control, aimed at maximizing the utilization of all available resources to enhance system efficiency. Various approaches, including static, heuristics-based, traditional dynamic, and metaheuristic-based algorithms, have been utilized for effective load balancing. However, due to the absence of a best-fit applicable solution, the challenge persists. This systematic review aims to investigate the application of the Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) method, along with its proposed variations, in achieving an even distribution of incoming traffic with efficient resource utilization.

Index Terms: Cloud Computing, Load Balancing, Metaheuristics, Particle Swarm Optimization, Review.

I. INTRODUCTION

Presently, scientific scholars as well as commercial researchers have made Cloud Computing an increasingly prevalent field of technological advancement [1]. It has a pay-as-you-go concept and is a distributed computer system based on the Internet [2], and [3]. Cloud Computing is an approach that enables platforms by hybridization of parallel and distributed computing to flexibly assign resources. Data centers are seriously clustered with high-speed computers and networking equipment in a cloud computing infrastructure. Because user requirements are always dynamic and the resources available along with the requested services are frequently varied, it is customary that the amount of traffic in clusters is not evenly distributed. Cloud provides different types of services, they can be either in the form of software, infrastructure, or platform. These services can be deployed through various cloud models, including public, private, hybrid, and community clouds. [4-7]. Assigning resources manually becomes a complex task due to the utilization of numerous resources in the cloud environment [5], and [8]. The underutilized or overutilized computing hosts are mostly due to the rapid growth of technology and the rise in the production of online information throughout the period. Resource overload or underutilization in cloud computing typically stems from an uneven distribution of workloads across hosts or data centers, leading to diminished overall system performance. Ensuring a balanced load across all hosts is essential for enhancing the performance of cloud infrastructure. In many cloud applications, the completion speed of a specific task can

vary from one node to another due to differences in the computational capacity of the hosts. Therefore, achieving effective load balancing is a key challenge in a cloud computing environment. A large queue forms on the server and lengthens the response time if multiple requests for resource utilization are made simultaneously by various users. There is a great need for such techniques that must balance the system and distribute the incoming traffic to all available VMs to avoid these situations [9]. In the field of optimal load distribution within the Cloud Computing environment, most of the surveys analyzed can be categorized into different types: taxonomy-based surveys, comparative surveys, and surveys focusing on static and dynamic load balancing approaches [10-13].

The primary focus of the systematic review being discussed is centered on the application of Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO), a Swarm Intelligence (SI) based approach, used for dynamically distributing the load in Cloud-based environments. The remaining paper is structured in the following way: Section II comprises an overview of load balancing in a Cloud environment and its importance, Section III of the document introduces the concept of metaheuristics, delving into its application and necessity in the realm of load balancing. Section IV is dedicated to presenting Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) and its variations that are applicable to load-balancing tasks. Following this, Section V showcases the enhancements in Quality of Service (QoS) parameters observed in recent literature because of employing the PSO algorithm. The document concludes with a discussion and outlines potential directions for future work in this area.

II. LOAD BALANCER IN CLOUD COMPUTING

Load balancing fundamentally involves evenly distributing workload across available IT resources. Its primary goal is to ensure continuous service delivery, effectively utilizing resources without overburdening any application, even in the event of service failures. This process not only aims to minimize delays in processing jobs but also focuses on optimizing resource usage to enhance system performance in a cost-effective manner. Moreover, load balancing provides the flexibility needed for services that might scale up or down in the future, requiring adjustments in IT resource allocation [14].

A. Background of Load Balancing

In unbalanced clouds, a two-stage load balancing modeling approach modified version of the design provided by Gupta et al. [14] is offered for attaining the optimal load reduction as shown in figure I.

Figure I: A Load Balancing Architecture, Comprises of 2 Stages

This paradigm abstracts the Virtual Machine (VM) controller and virtual machine supervisor. Physical Machine (PM) tier load balancing is used for the first stage, and VM level load balancing is used for the second stage. This can be concluded as two types of task migration i.e., intra and inter VM task migration.

User requests that necessitate computational resources to execute are turned into user requests by the request producer. Datacenter management is carried out by the task manager. The load balancer analyses a specific user workload to determine which VM to assign. The first level load balancer equalizes the load on each particular PM by

distributing it among its associated VMs. By using a second-stage load balancer, the traffic is evenly split amongst numerous VMs running on distinct PMs.

B. Elements Involved in Load Distribution

Organizing and assigning jobs to cloud resources in accordance with their demands is the effort involved in Cloud Computing [15]. The following elements are integral to the procedure involved in the design of a load balancer:

- **Determining the Needs of User Requests:**

The resource(s) requirements of the user requests that will be scheduled to be executed on a VM are determined during this stage.

- **Determining the VM Resource Information:**

This checks the current status of a VM's resource information. It displays the amount of resources that have not been allocated, as well as the virtual machine's current resource usage. Based on this information, the VM can be classified as balanced, overburdened, or underloaded according to a specific criterion.

- **Scheduling of Tasks:**

After a VM's resource information is recognized, a scheduling technique schedules workloads to the adequate resources on the optimally available VMs.

- **Resource Distribution:**

The resources are given to carry out the scheduled operations. A resource allocation method is being employed to achieve this. Numerous scheduling and distribution strategies have been presented in the research [16], and [17]. The effectiveness of the work scheduling and distribution plan has an impact on how reliable the load-balancing technique performs [18].

- **Migration of Task and Virtual Machine:**

Without the key migration phase, the idea of even distribution of load in the cloud is of no use. There are 2 kinds of migration: VM transfer and task migration depending on the entity under consideration. The migration of a VM from one host to a different one in order to address the overloading problem is known as VM migration, which can be further separated into dynamic and static VM migration. Task migration, which comes in two variants, is the process of moving tasks between virtual machines; and task transfer between and within VMs [19-21]. There have been many different migration strategies put out in the literature [22].

C. Need for Load Balancing

Amazon is using its own load balancer, but still, when the user requests are increased exponentially, they are not routed to targets due to high network congestion. Therefore, cloud services need load balancing.

The workload can be divided through load balancing in accordance with the resources offered. Its objective is to maintain continuous response by making available and disposing of application versions and making appropriate use of resources in the scenario that any service component

fails [23]. Reduced response time for operations and optimal resource utilization boosts device performance at a lower cost attributable to load balancing. It also seeks to assure sustainability and adaptability for operations whose scale will increase soon and require increased services in terms of various resources to assist any given service, as well as to prioritize those operations that must be done immediately in contrast to others. The capacity of load balancing to reduce energy usage, prevent bottlenecks, offer maintenance, and satisfy QoS requirements is another key reason for adapting it [24].

D. Performance Metrics of a Load Balancer

Enhancing the efficiency of the cloud with respect to Quality of Service (QoS) characteristics is the main objective of load-balancing techniques. Consequently, the metrics that ensure an improvement in the system's effectiveness must be included in the load-balancing methodology. The factors/parameters that follow the load balancing efficiency (i.e., key performance indicators) are listed below: [25], and [26].

The quality parameters mentioned are as follows:

- **Response Time (RT):**

This parameter indicates the speed at which the cloud responds to a client's request. A shorter response time is desirable as it enhances the overall user experience.

- **Throughput (T):**

This measures the rate at which customer queries or requests are processed, indicating the efficiency of the system.

- **MakeSpan (MS):**

As a Quality of Service (QoS) parameter, MakeSpan refers to the total time taken to complete a specified set of user requests. This metric is crucial for assessing the overall efficiency of the system in handling tasks.

- **Degree of Imbalance (DoI):**

A crucial QoS parameter pertains to the extent of disparity or imbalance in the distribution of workloads or tasks among the resources available within a cloud infrastructure.

- **Resource Utilization (RU):**

This measures the degree to which resources in the Cloud datacenter are being used, indicating the efficiency of resource allocation and consumption.

- **Convergence (C):**

In the context of workload scheduling, convergence as a Quality of Service (QoS) parameter refers to reaching a point in the problem space where an objective function is optimized, signifying the effectiveness of the scheduling process.

III. METAHEURISTIC ALGORITHMS

In various domains such as engineering, biological informatics, operations research, and geophysical sciences,

there's an escalating prevalence of optimization challenges. Similarly, the field of information technology is also witnessing growth in such problems. While many of these optimization issues are NP-hard, implying they cannot be solved in polynomial time unless NP (Non-Polynomial) is equivalent to P (Polynomial), in practical scenarios, this often isn't the case [27]. Consequently, precise mathematical methods are typically only feasible for small-scale instances. Rather than conceding defeat, researchers have turned to alternative approaches (optimal strategies) capable of delivering satisfactory solutions within a reasonable amount of effort. These strategies fall into two categories: heuristics and metaheuristics. One significant distinction between the two is that heuristics are more specific to certain problems, while metaheuristics are more universally applicable. As a result, while heuristics can be highly effective for specific scenarios, they often lack the versatility to address a broader range of problems. [28], and [29]. Fred Glover coined the term "Metaheuristic" in 1986 to describe a type of heuristic technique that is not specific to any particular problem [30].

Metaheuristics are characterized by their robust search strategies, which are a balance of two key searching attributes: exploration and exploitation. Exploration involves venturing into new search regions, thereby broadening the search scope. On the other hand, exploitation focuses on thoroughly searching areas around the most promising solutions found so far. These two elements - exploration and exploitation - form the core characteristics of meta-heuristic algorithms [31], and [32]. Metaheuristic algorithms possess several distinctive features, contributing to their effectiveness in solving complex problems:

- **Inspiration from Nature:**

Their primary motivation comes from natural phenomena.

- **Scientific and Biological Foundations:**

They are based on principles derived from scientific research, biological processes, and evolutionary mechanisms.

- **Stochastic Elements:**

Metaheuristics prominently utilize stochastic (random) components in their processes.

- **Usage of Random Variables:**

They employ random variables to diversify the search process.

- **Gradient-Independent:**

These algorithms do not rely on gradient information, making them suitable for a wider range of problems.

- **Diverse Problem-Solving Approaches:**

Metaheuristics apply various strategies to find the most optimal solution to a problem.

The ability of metaheuristic algorithms to handle complex issues requiring cooperation among various agents has made them particularly attractive to researchers [10]. This

interest is evident in the development and application of several metaheuristic algorithms, including Particle Swarm Optimization, Genetic Algorithm, Grey Wolf Optimization, Ant Colony Optimization, Water Wave Algorithm, and Glowworm Swarm Optimization [33]. These distinct optimization techniques have been successfully implemented in practice for a variety of optimization challenges [30], and [34].

A. Metaheuristic-based Load Balancer's Algorithm in Cloud Environment

The main challenge with load balancers in the backdrop of Cloud Computing is giving VMs a sufficient load so that none of them are overloaded or underloaded. Furthermore, the jobs must be given to the VM that can manage them. Numerous heuristics and metaheuristics are used to optimize VM throughput and address the scheduling problem of distributing incoming traffic to VMs. Numerous heuristics, including Prediction-based Earliest Finish Time, Performance Efficient Task Scheduling, and Heterogeneity-based Earliest Finish Time, were previously suggested to achieve the lowest time and cost for carrying out the activities [35-37]. The load-balancing challenge, nonetheless, involves multiple goals. The main goal is to divide up tasks throughout the available VMs in a way that minimizes the corresponding over or underutilization of resources [38], and the additional goal is to maximize resource utilization while reducing response time and cost. Therefore, metaheuristics algorithms are best fit to solve the load balancing issue as they have the nature to solve multi-objective problems [39]. Padhy et al. [40] presented an enhanced load-balancing method based on genetic algorithms. For a given mapping, a dynamic genetic algorithm executes selection, crossover, and mutation several times. This tactic aims to reduce the MakeSpan of the task set while balancing the load and speeding up response time. The recommended algorithm performs significantly better in terms of average execution time, MakeSpan, and resource utilization than the load balancing algorithm inspired by the Artificial Bee Colony (ABC), weighted RR, and First Come First Serve algorithms. Amer et al. [41] presented a novel hybrid multiple-purpose approach for solving the scheduling problem that utilizes Ant Colony Optimization and Spider Monkey Optimization. The objective function that was created considers multiple variables including resource utilization, energy consumption, execution time, and cost. Kaliappan et al. [42] presented another efficient hybrid technique to improve load balancing. This technique integrates PSO and Ant Colony Optimization for efficient task scheduling. The proposed method successfully reduces the downtime compared to other techniques.

IV. STANDARD PSO ALGORITHM AND ITS VARIANTS USED FOR LOAD BALANCING IN CLOUD COMPUTING

This section reviews the basic PSO-based load-balancing algorithm along with its variants.

A. Standard PSO-based Load Balancing Algorithm

The Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) technique fundamentally involves initializing positions and velocities

for each particle in the swarm, calculating their fitness values, and then iteratively updating their positions and velocities. Each particle represents a potential solution within the search space, with its position changing in each iteration based on velocity updates. The effectiveness of this search and optimization process is significantly influenced by several control parameters: Inertia Weight (w), which balances between global and local search capabilities; Number of Particles in the Population, affecting the swarm's diversity; Number of Iterations, dictating the duration of the optimization process; Self-Confidence Factor ($C1$), reflecting a particle's reliance on its own best position; and Swarm's Confidence Factor ($C2$), indicating the influence of the best position known by the swarm. These parameters collectively shape the PSO's ability to navigate and optimize within the search space [43].

The PSO's operations are shown in the pseudo-code (see table I). To get over PSO's drawbacks of inadequate accuracy and rapid convergence, some PSO advancements for load balancing have also been presented.

Table I: Pseudo-Code of PSO [45]

```

For each particle [Start]
  Initialize particle.
Do
  For each particle [Fitness]
    Calculate the fitness value.
    If the fitness value is better than the best
    fitness value (pβest) in history.
      Set the current value as the new pβest.
  End for
  Choose the particle with the best fitness value of all the
  particles as the gβest. [Selection]
  For each particle

    Calculate particle velocity according to Equation
    (a).

     $v[] = v[] + c1 * rand() * (p\beta est[] - present []) + c2$ 
     $* rand() * (g\beta est[] - present [])$  ----- Equation (a)

    Update particle position according to Equation (b).

     $present[] = present[] + v[]$  ----- Equation (b)

  End for a loop.

While maximum iterations or minimum error criteria
are not attained [End]

```

B. Task-based System Load Balancing using PSO Algorithm

Ramezani et al. [44] suggest using PSO to implement a task-oriented solution for the challenge of optimal load distribution solution that transfers only the unallocated tasks from an overcrowded VM, as opposed to migrating the full overloaded VM, to achieve the best load balancing. This research has developed an optimization model that

uses PSO to transfer these additional jobs to the new host VMs. The findings from the simulation showed that, in comparison to conventional load balancing methods, the suggested solution greatly reduces the execution time. Additionally, there is no need to employ the VM pre-copy procedure, and the overloaded VMs won't be suspended during the migration operation in the proposed technique. As a result, VM downtime and the chance that a customer may lose their most recent activity are also avoided.

C. Random-Forest Optimization-based PSO Algorithm

Bala and Kumar [46], use Random-Forest Optimization and PSO to distribute the load among the cloud platforms' available resources. The Random Forest method is used to create random schedules. Cloud Computing environment receives scheduling requests and executes them. PSO is used to locate the resources if they aren't accessible through the present VMs. Simulation results show that the proposed algorithm outperforms in terms of MakeSpan, response time, and degree of imbalance.

D. Improved PSO (iPSO) using Random Sampling

To increase convergence, Sun et al. [47] proposed an improved version of PSO. The approach of random selection for control parameters is used in the suggested research to boost randomization and update the particle's location and velocity. After the acceleration variables have been chosen in their specific interval, the sampling range for the inertia weight is determined to guarantee convergence.

Additionally, the stochastic adjustment approach is presumable on each dimension for a population's core value to make use of particle dimensional information to improve velocity and position. The experimental findings have demonstrated that, as opposed to standard PSO, the proposed method increases the accuracy to converge.

E. Amalgamative iPSO and Firefly Algorithm

A framework predicated on the hybrid Improved PSO and Firefly method was presented by Golchi et al. [48]. This method combines the Firefly algorithm and Improved PSO. Both algorithms have high sensitivity to initial factors and strong convergence rates, but slow down as they approach the optimal point in the search space. Hybridization aims to enhance the QoS parameters. The Firefly algorithm is employed to establish the best preliminary population, while iPSO is utilized for optimal task allocation. The objective is to achieve optimal response time, turnaround time, CPU utilization, and memory utilization.

F. α PSO Load Balancing Algorithm

R. M. Alguliyev et al. [45] presented a PSO-based load balancing system called α PSO that deals with the incoming tasks (i.e. task-based distribution). The technique offers an ideal transfer of workloads from overloaded VMs to corresponding s in the Cloud environment. The recommended optimization strategy's targeted objective functions are to minimize the tasks' execution and migration time. The proposed approach is experimentally tested. Simulations based on the suggested approach identified the optimal approach for job scheduling and equal assigning tasks to VMs and less time-consuming was achieved for the task allocation procedures.

G. Hybrid ABC and PSO

ABC and PSO are the two components of the hybrid algorithm that Thanka et al. [49] proposed. The suggested approach improves job scheduling in a Cloud context by offering reduced time, cost, and resource usage while balancing the load. The results are also presented by using a simulation tool. These results prove that the suggested technique outperforms when compared to the conventional ABC and standard PSO in terms of MakeSpan, resource utilization, and degree of imbalance.

H. A Novel PSO-based Load Balancing

The suggested methodology of the novel technique is divided into two stages [50]: Considering a total number of 100 particles, the standard PSO is utilized in the first stage. The population from the first stage is subjected to the best mutation, and the mutated products are used to populate the initial stage. The requests are distributed to an overloaded VM considering the capacity for processing and utilization of the VM to produce the remaining particles employing a deterministic technique. The workload of the VM is updated upon the allocation of tasks. This method calculates and stores the likelihood of job assignment for each VM. The virtual machine with the greatest possible probability receives the task. The suggested algorithm outperforms the other algorithms in terms of MakeSpan and resource utilization.

I. Discrete PSO-based Static Load Balancing Algorithm

To address the multi-objective problems with load balancing, Mia et al. [51] suggested an adaptive PSO-based static load balancing method. The individual best locations of the particles are updated using optimal solutions kept in the global records, and a probability- and similarity-based discretization technique referred to as PSO is suggested to update the particle's velocity and positioning vectors. The findings revealed that, in comparison to the state-of-the-art in this field, the suggested algorithm substantially boosted the convergence and variety of the incoming traffic while effectively decreasing the degree of imbalance.

J. Modified PSO Load Balancing Algorithm

To schedule jobs across the available Cloud resources in a way that minimizes MakeSpan and maximizes resource utilization, Pradhan and Bisoy [52] developed modified PSO task scheduling. This is accomplished by ensuring that the tasks and resources within the data center are properly informed. The main goal of the suggested technique is to reduce wait times and maximize resource utilization in Cloud Computing by scheduling all incoming tasks to the available VMs as efficiently as achievable. In this approach, the resource allocation technique is the main emphasis of the mapping, which is done with PSO to manage the resources in a way that ensures no job is left in the buffer and that the overall execution time is reduced. The entire model is divided into numerous buffers that each contain distinct types of tasks and resource knowledge, allowing for the optimization of resource allocation and accuracy strategies.

K. Multi-Swarm PSO for Task Scheduling

Liu et al. [53] offered a load-balancing-based Multi-Swarm Particle Swarm Optimization work scheduling strategy. The goal of the suggested method is to decrease response and maximum completion times for job scheduling. It enhances particle swarms' fitness evaluation capabilities to make load balancing easier. The rate of particles' convergence and search effectiveness can both be increased by the novel adaptive inertia weight and initiation method implementation. The Multi-Swarm architecture, meantime, can minimize the issue of particles entering local optimums. The suggested methodology outperforms when it is empirically tested using the task-specific dataset made available by Alibaba's data center and evaluated with other benchmark techniques.

L. Hybrid fast Converging PSO for Load Balancing

Reshan et al. [54] in order to maintain the servers' uptime proposed a hybrid fast-converging load distribution technique that achieved globally optimal rapid convergence. The Grey Wolf method integrates with PSO. Grey Wolf is simple to construct because it doesn't rely significantly on controlling variables. Due to the rapid convergence, the scheduling method is adaptable enough to consider several requests that are competing for the same virtual machine. This rigorous thinking is also supported by the simulation's results, and the proposed algorithm performs as anticipated while outperforming state-of-the-art algorithms in terms of overall response time, cost, and convergence of PSO (along with its various versions).

M. Intelligent PSO for Load Balancing Algorithm

Ghafir et al. [55] propose a PSO-inspired intelligent approach for efficient load balancing. The technique utilizes an improved PSO algorithm with Pareto dominance in order to provide enhanced quality of service, efficiency, scalability, low response time, and optimum bilateral transposed convolution filtering. Furthermore, due to

ineffective VM placement among Physical Machines, current VM migration procedures lead to violations of service level agreements. A Double-Deep Q proximal structure that includes a feedback controller has been suggested as a solution to these problems. The selection model's double weight set in the web-based and offline updating procedure keeps the cloud service level agreement running well. Additionally, in complex scenarios with process instruction combining, both centralized and decentralized controller algorithms fail due to a single point of failure and coordination issues.

N. Hybrid Dragonfly and PSO for Load Balancing

Mohapatra et al. [56] devised a framework that combines the Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) and Dragonfly (DF) algorithms to achieve optimal resource management for load balancing. The Dragonfly algorithm and PSO are used to analyze the efficiency of the suggested method. The effectiveness is assessed using several metrics, including response time and best fitness value, which are varied by altering the user base and response time. There are different user bases of 50, 100, 500, and 1000. For performing comparative analysis, the size of the user bases is changed to monitor how well the algorithm is performing. It is noted that for load balancing, the suggested strategy performs better than the other approaches. The comparative advantage of PSO over a significant Dragonfly algorithm is also supported by statistical analysis and conventional testing. The hybrid strategy offers reduced response time in a dynamic environment.

The QoS parameters determined by various PSO-based approaches that have been suggested for the period of 2014–2024 are summarized in table II. Furthermore, some areas of improvement in the context of PSO-based load balancing in cloud computing are also identified from the systematic review. These areas of improvement are summarized in table III along with the description

Table II: Summary of the QoS Parameters Targeted by Various PSO-based Approaches during the Period of 2014–2024

Reference	Year	Algorithm	RT	ET	DoI	Cost	MS	C	RU	CPU Utilization	Memory Utilization
[44]	2014	Task-based PSO-Load Balancer	X	✓	X	✓	X	X	X	X	X
[46]	2017	Random forest optimization-based PSO	✓	X	✓	X	✓	X	X	X	X
[47]	2019	Improved PSO using Random Sampling	X	X	X	X	X	✓	X	X	X
[48]	2019	Hybrid improved PSO and firefly algorithm	✓	✓	X	X	X	X	X	✓	✓
[45]	2019	α PSO Load Balancing Algorithm	X	✓	X	X	X	✓	X	X	X
[49]	2019	ABC and PSO-based Load Balancing	X	X	✓	X	✓	X	✓	X	X
[50]	2021	A Novel PSO-based Load Balancing	X	X	X	X	✓	X	✓	✓	✓
[51]	2021	Discrete PSO-based Static Resource Distribution	X	X	✓	X	X	✓	X	X	X
[52]	2022	Modified PSO	X	✓	X	X	✓	X	✓	X	X
[53]	2023	Multi-Swarm PSO For Task Scheduling	✓	✓	X	X	X	X	X	X	X

[54]	2023	Hybrid fast Converging PSO for Load Balancing	✓	✗	✗	✓	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗
[55]	2024	Intelligent PSO	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗
[56]	2024	Hybrid Dragonfly and PSO	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗

Table III: Areas of Improvements in the Context of PSO-based Load Balancing in Cloud Computing

Area of Improvement	Description	Recommendation	Impact
Rate of Convergence	The PSO-based algorithms still need improvement in convergence in the case of dynamic and large-scale platform	Design improved hybrid algorithms to handle parameter adjustment dynamically for optimal convergence	Improved performance with real-time enhanced convergence
Practical Validation	The existing PSO-based algorithms lack in implementing the proposed load balancing algorithms in real-world Cloud environments	Conduct the experimental tests in operational Cloud infrastructure to get more clear insights	Improved reliability and wider adoption
Complex Tradeoffs Ignorance	The existing PSO based algorithms state of the art algorithms lack in discussing the tradeoffs that exist between various QoS parameters	Develop algorithms while deliberately considering the existing tradeoffs	More effective resource management with optimal utilization of backend services
Considering Security	The PSO-based load balancing techniques ignore security parameters while developing a load balancer	Integrate security validations while developing load balancing method to ensure integrity while task transfer from one resource to another	Improves the safety of services and is useful in highly confidential applications

V. CONCLUSION

With the development of modern tools, novel techniques, and a large rise in traffic, load balancing is becoming increasingly important. As the flow of traffic patterns becomes unpredictable, the problem gets worse. Consequently, a workable solution is required. The study provides information on a few PSO versions that can be utilized to balance load effectively. Although numerous academics have suggested PSO, convergence analysis is the portion that receives the least attention.

To discover the best possible solution for efficient load distribution, the convergence rate must be increased because it is something that is highly required because of high user retention. The systematic review attempts to understand the feasibility and application of the PSO technique for load balancing in Cloud systems through a thorough and rigorous investigation of the available literature. These are the main findings that are observed during the detailed study: The research shows that the PSO method is a viable and efficient method for managing loads in Cloud Computing. Numerous studies have demonstrated that PSO can efficiently optimize job distribution and allocation of resources to improve load balancing in cloud-based environments. Employing the PSO technique for load balancing has been shown in multiple investigations to significantly increase system performance measures like response time, memory utilization, and resource utilization. This indicates that PSO may be able to improve the general effectiveness and functionality of cloud infrastructure. PSO has shown its flexibility and resilience to deal with changing and erratic workload changes. The approach works well for real-time load distribution in Cloud-based environments because it can quickly adjust to changing environments.

According to the literature review, there is considerable study being done on the PSO algorithm's adaptability in large-scale cloud settings. While PSO has shown potential in small-scale configurations, more research is required to evaluate how well it performs in large-scale, extremely complex cloud infrastructures. The advent of hybrid load-balancing strategies that integrate PSO with other optimization methods or heuristics is highlighted. These hybrid techniques attempt to take advantage of the advantages of various algorithms to offer improved load-balancing alternatives. There are still several issues and unaddressed problems in the field of load balancing utilizing PSO in Cloud Computing. Choosing the proper variables, managing multi-objective optimization, and dealing with security issues are a few of them. Although the encouraging outcomes were produced by several cutting-edge PSO-based load-balancing techniques, the review reveals that there are some unaddressed research issues in the literature. These shortcomings include the absence of empirical studies in actual cloud systems, the necessity for performance metric standardization, and the requirement for comparative research with other load-balancing methods.

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Authors Contributions

All the authors equally contributed to this study.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest and confirm that this work is original and not plagiarized from any other source, i.e., electronic or print media. The information

obtained from all of the sources is properly recognized and cited below.

Data Availability Statement

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